

Utilising a Clustering Model to Understand Patterns in Crime for Selected Nigerian Regions.

Author

Oreofe Jason Jolaolu. Msc. Data Science

ORCID iD: 0009-0004-2039-2686

Abstract

Nigeria is a country that has experienced a significant level of crime and insecurity, which has immensely disrupted the welfare and economy of the Nigerian people. To help combat crime and the effects of crime, an efficient, scalable crime classification system that identifies and segments patterns in the severity or level of crime in a region (based on crime incidents, population, and crime rates) using historical data is recommended.

This research work specifically reviews and analyses data related to crime against persons, crime against property, and crime against lawful authorities within various Nigerian regions. The study also utilises a k-means algorithm to classify the severity or level of crime in different states and regions. This will assist security agencies in the deployment of adequate strategies for preventing or managing incidents related to highlighted clusters, before they occur or spread to other locations in grouped data points.

Keywords: machine learning, k-means, clustering, crime, police force

1.0 Introduction

Crime is a multifaceted topic that has been investigated for centuries. It encompasses a wide range of actions that are deemed illegal by society. The definition of crime can vary across different cultures and historical periods. While there are different viewpoints on what constitutes a crime or criminal activity, at its core, crime refers to any act that violates established laws within a specific jurisdiction (Farmer, 2008). These established laws serve to maintain social order, protect individual rights, and ensure the smooth functioning of society. Crime can also be referred to as acts or activities that cause harm to a person, people or society (Ashworth & Jeremy, 2013). These activities are punishable under applicable law (Martin, 2003), which varies from region to region. Examples of criminal activities include minor offenses like theft or vandalism to more serious acts such as murder or fraud.

Throughout history, the understanding of crime has evolved. During the enlightenment period, thinkers like Cesare Beccaria advocated for a more rational approach to crime and punishment (Ranasinghe, 2022). It was argued that laws should be based on reason rather than religious beliefs or arbitrary power. This shift in thinking helped to develop modern legal systems that focus on principles such as proportionality, prevention, and rehabilitation.

Defining what constitutes a crime remains complex due to cultural differences and changing societal norms. What may be considered criminal in one country may be permissible in another due to variations in legislation or cultural practices (Fattah, 1997).

In modern times, crime has become a social problem and not just a conflict between individuals. As early as the 17th century, writers like Thomas Hobbes viewed crime as a social problem (Sumner, 2004). Societal adaptations such as urbanisation and industrialisation in the 19th century made crime an immediate problem for society, leading to government intervention to combat crime and the establishment of criminology as a distinct field.

Criminology is the field concerned with the formal study of crime and criminal activities (Davies & Rowe, 2022). It is an established field that examines what crime means to criminals and the impact criminal activity has on people and property (Braithwaite, 2000).

Various concepts in criminology provide different descriptions and explanations of crime, including subculture theory, strain theory, differential association, and social ecology theory (Siegel, 2015). Criminology experts study criminal psychology, criminal law, crime prevention and crime statistics.

Over time, information and statistics on crime in a particular jurisdiction was collected in the form of crime estimates. Methods for collecting crime statistics can vary, even between different jurisdictions or regions within the same country. It is important to note that under-reporting of crimes is common, particularly in developing countries (Eze et. al, 2019).

The purpose of this study is to analyse data related to crime, deploy a machine learning model to identify/segment patterns in criminal activities (using available data), and proffer data driven recommendations to effectively combat crime within various regions in Nigeria based on the intelligence derived from the analysis and modelling.

2.0 Literature Review

Nigeria is a West African country with diverse geography, climate and population. Currently, it is the most populous country in Africa (Statista, 2022). The history of crime in Nigeria is a complex and multi-layered issue that spans centuries. In pre-colonial Nigeria, crime which was sometimes referred to as “abomination” was combated primarily through traditional justice systems (Saleh-Hanna et. al, 2008). Crimes such as theft, assault and murder could incur penalties such as fines or banishment from the community. However, with the emergence of European colonial powers in the 19th century, new forms of acts that could be classified as crime and punishments for crime emerged (Saleh-Hanna et. al, 2008).

In the post-independence period, Nigeria experienced a sharp rise in organised crime due to political instability and economic inequality. The oil boom of the 1970s further exacerbated these problems as wealth was concentrated among a few people and poverty increased (Ellis, 2016). Organised crime in Nigeria includes the activities of fraudsters, bandits (e.g. looting and kidnapping on major highways), and drug traffickers, etc. Nigerian criminal gangs rose to prominence in the 1980s, largely due to the globalisation of the world economy and the high levels of lawlessness and corruption in the country. Criminal organisations in Nigeria generally do not follow the mafia model of other groups. They tend to be less formal and more organised along family and ethnic lines, making them less vulnerable to infiltration by law enforcement. While criminal gangs appear to be independent organisations operating on a smaller scale, the nature and activities of crime are diverse in nature (Williams, 2014).

For example, the illegal gangs known as area boys, are loosely organised gangs of street children and youths who roam the streets of Lagos State, Nigeria. They extort money from passers-by, public transport operators and drug dealers, sell illegal drugs, act as informal security guards and do other “jobs” for money (Heap, 2010).

The government is primarily concerned with the safety and well-being of citizens and implements this through a combination of institutions. These institutions include primary security agencies such as the army, police, paramilitary services, and intelligence service. Among these agencies, the police is the main law enforcement institution that carries out liaison activities between state and society, and it is termed as “the most symbolic formal actors of social control” (Cao et al., 2016).

Research has identified significant gaps in the effectiveness of modern policing and the quality of policing in the face of growing security challenges (Hills, 2008). It is important for the Nigerian Police Force to leverage on machine learning models to combat crime, and improve public safety in Nigeria.

This study is a research effort leveraging on past and historical data, to identify patterns of occurrences of crime in the South-South, South West, South East, North East, North West and North Central regions of Nigeria. The outcome will help Nigerian law enforcement agents to leverage machine learning algorithms to draw various inferences from available data, enabling more accurate, data-driven decisions.

According to Khan et al. (2022), there are two significant crime classes which are violent & nonviolent. The study by Khan et al. (2022) utilised the Naive Bayes, Random Forest, and Gradient Boosting Decision Tree techniques. Also, the study indicated that Gradient Boosting Decision Tree prediction model is a reliable crime prediction model. In this study, crime is classified by the following categories: crime against persons, crime against property, and crime against lawful authorities.

3.0 Methodology

In this case study, the nature of crime has been broadly classified as: crime against persons, crime against property, and crime against lawful or constituted authority in Nigeria. The data points utilised includes: crime statistics related to offence against persons in Nigeria, crime statistics related to offence against property in Nigeria , crime statistics related to offence against lawful authority in Nigeria and population statistics for different states in Nigeria over a 1 year period. Crime and population statistics were retrieved from the National Bureau of Statistics and Nigeria Data Portal. The data was extensively reviewed to determine the following: existence of outliers, identification of duplicate or redundant data and existence of invalid data or typographical errors.

3.1 Crime Rate Analysis

Analysis was conducted to determine the crime rate in each (state/region) in Nigeria. This is the number of crimes reported and documented by law enforcement agents in Nigeria. To estimate the crime rate, we find the quotient of the number of reported crimes with respect to the population of the region, and the outcome or result is multiplied by one hundred thousand (100,000) Crime Rate = (Reported Crimes / Regional Population) * 100,000. Thus:

$$CR_r = ((RC_r) / (RP_r)) * 100,000$$

Crime Rate in a region/state = CR_r Reported Crime in a region/state = RC_r and Regional Population = RP_r . Crime Rate is a derived quantity and the tables below outline the crime rate for various states in Nigeria.

State	Crime Rate	Region	State	Crime Rate	Region
Abia	263.35	South East	Kano	16.07	North West
Adamawa	19.09	North East	Katsina	7.69	North West
Akwa Ibom	12.81	South South	Kebbi	1.98	North West
Anambra	2.30	South East	Kogi	3.26	North Central
Bauchi	3.00	North East	Kwara	8.74	North Central
Bayelsa	26.87	South South	Lagos	150.80	South West
Benue	7.51	North Central	Nasarawa	18.47	North Central
Borno	11.62	North East	Niger	10.15	North Central
Cross River	24.55	South South	Ogun	9.93	South West
Delta	58.45	South South	Ondo	27.44	South West
Ebonyi	44.26	South East	Osun	6.76	South West
Edo	25.31	South South	Oyo	13.49	South West
Ekiti	10.08	South West	Plateau	17.52	North Central
Enugu	21.20	South East	Rivers	6.39	South South
FCT	33.19	North Central	Sokoto	15.33	North West
Gombe	12.53	North East	Taraba	17.93	North East
Imo	16.51	South East	Yobe	11.14	North East
Jigawa	5.92	North West	Zamfara	3.74	North West
Kaduna	4.67	North West			

Table 1.0 Crime Rates for crime against persons in Nigeria

State	Crime Rate	Region	State	Crime Rate	Region
Abia	62.24	South East	Kano	25.34	North West
Adamawa	33.09	North East	Katsina	11.52	North West
Akwa Ibom	10.82	South South	Kebbi	2.39	North West
Anambra	18.63	South East	Kogi	2.48	North Central
Bauchi	2.85	North East	Kwara	16.47	North Central
Bayelsa	36.88	South South	Lagos	199.11	South West
Benue	26.12	North Central	Nasarawa	19.06	North Central
Borno	15.48	North East	Niger	24.17	North Central
Cross River	29.95	South South	Ogun	10.46	South West
Delta	54.90	South South	Ondo	45.85	South West
Ebonyi	96.76	South East	Osun	10.92	South West
Edo	29.44	South South	Oyo	23.79	South West
Ekiti	13.08	South West	Plateau	44.50	North Central
Enugu	25.19	South East	Rivers	15.10	South South
FCT	116.72	North Central	Sokoto	32.45	North West
Gombe	29.84	North East	Taraba	32.54	North East
Imo	12.89	South East	Yobe	16.24	North East
Jigawa	6.81	North West	Zamfara	7.04	North West
Kaduna	8.41	North West			

Table 2.0 Crime Rates for crime against property in Nigeria

State	Crime Rate	Region	State	Crime Rate	Region
Abia	7.30	South East	Kano	2.21	North West
Adamawa	1.22	North East	Katsina	0.74	North West
Akwa Ibom	6.90	South South	Kebbi	0.25	North West
Anambra	13.22	South East	Kogi	0.56	North Central
Bauchi	0.06	North East	Kwara	0.78	North Central
Bayelsa	3.99	South South	Lagos	56.25	South West
Benue	1.92	North Central	Nasarawa	5.27	North Central
Borno	0.05	North East	Niger	13.57	North Central
Cross River	1.45	South South	Ogun	10.29	South West
Delta	12.91	South South	Ondo	6.19	South West
Ebonyi	5.28	South East	Osun	1.15	South West
Edo	10.66	South South	Oyo	0.59	South West
Ekiti	2.83	South West	Plateau	0.05	North Central
FCT	1.09	North Central	Sokoto	0.52	North West
Gombe	1.01	North East	Taraba	1.08	North East
Imo	1.48	South East	Yobe	2.67	North East
Jigawa	0.81	North West	Zamfara	0.71	North West
Kaduna	0.05	North West			

Table 3.0 Crime Rates for crime against lawful authority in Nigeria

Fig 1.0 Statistical Crime Rate Maps.

Fig 2.0 Crime Rate Bar Charts (Crime Rate vs. Geo Political Region)

Findings and results from quantitative analysis of the dataset is outlined in the table below.

Query	Result
State with highest crime rate for crime against persons	Abia State
State with highest crime rate for crime against property:	Lagos State
State with highest crime rate for crime against lawful authority	Lagos State
State with lowest crime rate for crime against persons	Kebbi State
State with lowest crime rate for crime against property	Kebbi State
State with lowest crime rate for crime against lawful authority	Plateau State
Geo political region with highest crime rate for crime against persons	South East
Geo political region with highest crime rate for crime against property	South West
Geo political region with highest crime rate for crime against lawful authority:	South West
Geo political region with lowest crime rate for crime against persons	North West
Geo political region with lowest crime rate for crime against property	North West
Geo political region with lowest crime rate for crime against lawful authority	North West

Table 4.0 Findings from Crime Rate Analysis

3.2 Modelling

The K-means clustering algorithm was utilised in this analysis. This is useful for clustering and discovering hidden patterns in data. The data points in the clusters are based on two features: crime rate and population. Utilising k-means clustering techniques offers a number of advantages such as simple implementation for different use cases, and adaptation to new patterns. It also provides alternatives for scaling to large or huge datasets and guarantees convergence,

Obtaining the optimal number of clusters is an important part of the k-means algorithm. A regularly used method for finding the optimum K value is the elbow method. To derive the optimal value for K, we can execute the K-means model across data for different values. When the K-means model was trained, the inertia was plotted based on different numbers of clusters. The results indicate that the inertia becomes more linear at K=3. We have fitted the k-means algorithm to this number of clusters and plotted the output clusters around this recommendation.

Fig 3.0 Finding optimal number of clusters with elbow method.

Fig 4.0 Clustering Outputs for Crime Rate/Population

3.3 Results

Regarding the clustering output for “crime against persons”, the yellow cluster has the highest population and a high crime rate. The green cluster indicates areas with a moderately high population, and a moderate crime rate, the purple cluster has the lowest population and a low crime rate. The data points are relatively close together, highlighting a consistent relationship between these two variables within this segment. In summary, the clusters suggest a general trend: higher population tends to correlate with higher crime rates. However, the yellow cluster outliers show this relationship isn't always linear. Some areas can have extremely high populations and crime rates, significantly deviating from the general pattern observed in the green and purple clusters.

The clustering output for the “crime against persons” scatter plot indicates the yellow cluster can be labelled as outliers compared to the bulk of the data points in the green and purple clusters. This cluster represents areas with exceptionally high populations and correspondingly the highest levels of property crime. These are distinct outliers from the rest of the dataset. This green segment consists of areas that, despite having relatively low to moderate populations, experience a moderate to significant level of property crime. There is a noticeable concentration of points in this group. This suggests other factors might be driving property crime in these locations.

Furthermore, this purple cluster represents areas with low populations, and correspondingly lower to moderate levels of property crime compared to the green and yellow clusters. This is the densest cluster, indicating many such areas in the dataset.

Lastly, the green clusters in the clustering outputs for “crime against authority” show areas with low population, and low to moderate crime against lawful authority. These are areas with small populations, and correspondingly the lowest levels of this specific crime type. The purple cluster is a significant cluster where even very small populations can experience moderate to substantial levels of crime against lawful authority. The crime levels here are notably higher than the green cluster, despite similar or only slightly larger populations. The yellow cluster indicates two distinct cases: a very low population area and a very high population area with exceptionally high crime against lawful authority.

High levels of crime against lawful authority can indicate serious societal problems, including challenges to the rule of law and a lack of trust in institutions.

3.4 Recommendations for combating crime and crime rate

- High levels of crime against lawful authority can indicate serious societal problems, including challenges to the rule of law, and a lack of trust in institutions. Strategies to address this challenge might have to include advanced policing, and may involve political dialogue, social programs, and reforms.
- Improving security awareness, community relationship and engagement between public and law enforcement agents in affected states and regions i.e Abia State, Lagos State, South East and South West Regions.
- Create incentives, publicly acknowledge citizens, and public officers that shun crime such bribery and corruption (crime against lawful authority).

- Strengthen the legislative, judiciary and law enforcement institutions to effectively combat and tackle grievous crimes such as kidnapping and terrorism in regions with high crime rates to serve as a deterrent other actors with criminal intentions
- Increase funding, manpower, logistics and infrastructural support (i.e. more police posts, training etc) for states and regions with high crime rates. A short term solution for regions or states that do not have adequate manpower or infrastructure is community policing which can help to maintain law and order at the local level
- More research and development efforts should be put into resolving socio economic challenges such as poverty and unemployment in areas with high crime rate to mitigate the propensity for people to commit crime.
- Lastly, vast improvements in data gathering capacity at national and local levels to ensure that insights are accurate and depict the reality regarding the subject matter.

4.0 Conclusion

Although machine learning and deep learning algorithms are effective in crime prediction, significant challenges remain. In addition to existing model-based explanation methods, it is important to also include causal explanations that focus on the cause-effect relationship between crime patterns and relevant characteristic variables. Additionally, to successfully apply machine learning and deep learning techniques to crime prediction, it is important to have access to current, high quality crime data.

When implementing machine learning in crime analysis, ethical considerations such as privacy and potential algorithm bias must also be taken into account. Crime prediction models often rely on personal information like demographics or criminal records. Protecting people's privacy when using this data is critical to maintaining public trust. Striking a balance between public safety and individual rights is a complex challenge. Because these technologies are used to predict individuals and communities, it is important to ensure that they do not perpetuate existing biases or lead to discrimination. Further research is also needed on the privacy implications of using these crime prediction technologies, including, among other things, the potential for data breaches and misuse of personal data.

Due to continuous social and technological developments, the complexity of crime is constantly evolving. It is important for governments and law enforcement agencies to focus on machine learning and deep learning techniques to effectively combat crime. To effectively analyse and detect the nature of crime patterns in Nigeria, it is recommended that resources are dedicated (at the national and regional levels) to effectively capture data, manage crime related datasets, enable research for building and deploying sophisticated and machine learning models for effective crime management in Nigeria.

5.0 References

- Adunbi, O. (2018). Organised Crime In Nigeria. *The Journal of African History*, 59(1), 168-170. doi:10.1017/S0021853718000270
- Alkheder, S., Alrukaibi, F. & Aiash, A. (2022). Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and Bayesian Network for prediction and analysis of GCC traffic accidents. *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*. 14. 1-9. 10.1007/s12652-022-04441-4.
- Antolos, D., Liu, D., Ludu, A. & Vincenzi, D. (2013). Burglary Crime Analysis Using Logistic Regression. 8018. 549-558. 10.1007/978-3-642-39226-9_60.
- Ashworth, A. & Horder, J. (2013). *Principles of Criminal Law* (7th ed.). Oxford University Press. ISBN 9780199672684.
- Bao, Y., Hilary, G., & Ke, B. (2020). Artificial Intelligence and Fraud Detection. *Social Science Research Network*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3738618>
- Braithwaite, J. (1 March 2000). "The New Regulatory State and the Transformation of Criminology". *British Journal of Criminology*. 40 (2): 222–238. doi:10.1093/bjc/40.2.222
- Burrell, J. (2016). How the machine ‘thinks’: Understanding opacity in machine learning algorithms. *Big Data & Society*, 3(1), 205395171562251. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951715622512>
- Bybee, A. N. (2012). *The Twenty-First Century Expansion of the Transnational Drug Trade in Africa*. Columbia University
- Cao L, Huang L. & Sun I. (2016). From authoritarian policing to democratic policing: a case study of Taiwan. *Policing and Society* 26(6): 642–658
- Carmona D. (2019), *The AI Organization*, O'Reilly Media, Inc.
- Cio, E. (2022). The scope of artificial intelligence in fighting cybercrime. ETCIO.com. Retrieved from <https://cio.economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/digital-security/the-scope-of-artificial-intelligence-in-fighting-cybercrime/92072000>
- Davies, P. & Rowe, M. (2022). *An introduction to criminology*. SAGE Publications.
- Ellis, S.(2016). *ORGANIZED CRIME IN NIGERIA - This Present Darkness: A History of Nigerian Organized Crime*. London and New York: Oxford University Press
- English, V. L. (2018). Judges now using artificial intelligence to rule on prisoners. VOA. Retrieved from <https://learningenglish.voanews.com/a/ai-used-by-judges-to-rule-on-prisoners/4236134.html>
- Eze, V., Diyoke, M. C. & Idoko I. (2019). Investigating the Impact of Crime Reporting on Crime Control in Gwagwalada Area Council Abuja North Central Nigeria. 10.5281/zenodo.3374028.
- Farmer, L. (2016) "Crime, definitions of", in Cane and Conaghan (editors), *The New Oxford Companion to Law*, Oxford University Press, 2008 (ISBN 978-0-19-929054-3), p. 263 (Google Books Archived 2016-06-04 at the Wayback Machine).
- Fattah, E. A. (1997). *Criminology: Past, Present and Future: A Critical Overview*. Palgrave Macmillan UK. ISBN 9781349258383.
- Hazlegreaves, S. (2021). *Public Safety and Smart Cities: How Assistive Ai will help*. Open Access Government. Retrieved from <https://www.openaccessgovernment.org/public-safety-and-smart-cities-how-assistive-ai-will-help/111615/>

- Hills, A. (2008). The dialectic of police reform in Nigeria. *The Journal of Modern African Studies* 46(2): 215–234
- Ikekpolo, W. O. (2016). Boko Haram: understanding the context. *Third World Quarterly* <https://doi.org/10.1080/01436597.2016.1177453>
- Jafri, R. & Arabnia, H. R. (2009) “A Survey of Face Recognition Techniques,” *Journal of Information Processing Systems*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 41–68, Jun. 2009, doi:10.3745/jips.2009.5.2.041
- Jenga, K. & Catal, C. & Kar, G. (2023) Machine learning in crime prediction. *J Ambient Intell Human Comput* 14, 2887–2913. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12652-023-04530-y>
- Jordan, M. I. & Mitchell, T. M. (2015). Machine learning: Trends, perspectives, and prospects. *Science*, 349(6245), 255–260. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaa8415>
- Khan, M. & Ali, A. & Alharbi, Y. (2022). Predicting and Preventing Crime: A Crime Prediction Model Using San Francisco Crime Data by Classification Techniques. *Complexity*. 2022. 1-13. 10.1155/2022/48304
- Khanam, M., Mahboob, T., Imtiaz, W., Ghafoor, H. & Sehar, R. (2015). A Survey on Unsupervised Machine Learning Algorithms for Automation, Classification and Maintenance. *International Journal of Computer Applications*. 119. 34-39. 10.5120/21131-4058.
- Kramer. S.N. (1954). "Ur-Nammu Law Code". *Orientalia*, 23 (1), 40.
- Kumar, A., Verma, A., Shinde, G., Sukhdeve, Y., & Lal, N. (2020). Crime Prediction Using K-Nearest Neighboring Algorithm. 2020 International Conference on Emerging Trends in Information Technology and Engineering (ic-ETITE), 1-4.
- Kumar, K.K., Kasiviswanadham, Y., Indira, D.V.S.N.V., Palesetti, P.P. & Ch.V. Bhargavi, (2021) Criminal face identification system using deep learning algorithm multi-task cascade neural network (MTCNN), *Materials Today: Proceedings*, Volume 80, Part 3, 2023, Pages 2406-2410, ISSN 2214-7853, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2021.06.373>.
- Lazarus, S., & Okolorie, G. U. (2019). "The bifurcation of the Nigerian cybercriminals: Narratives of the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) agents". *Telematics and Informatics*. 40: 14–26. doi:10.1016/j.tele.2019.04.009. S2CID 150113120.
- Martin, E.A. (2003). *Oxford Dictionary of Law* (7 ed.). Oxford: Oxford University Press. ISBN 978-0-19-860756-4.
- McCorduck, P. (2004), *Machines Who Think* (2nd ed.), Natick, MA: A. K. Peters, Ltd
- McDaniel, J. & Pease, K. (Eds.). (2021). *Predictive Policing and Artificial Intelligence* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429265365>
- Mehryar M., Afshin R., & Ameet Talwalkar (2012) *Foundations of Machine Learning*, The MIT Press ISBN 9780262018258.
- Menon, A., Singh, K., Kumar, R., & Sethi, R. & Rajpoot, A. (2023). Leveraging Facial Recognition Technology in Criminal Identification.
- Mohri, M., Rostamizadeh, A. & Talwalkar, A. (2012). *Foundations of Machine Learning*.
- Nasridinov, A., Ihm, S., & Park, Y. (2013). A Decision Tree-Based Classification Model for Crime Prediction. 253. 531-538. 10.1007/978-94-007-6996-0-56.
- National Bureau of Statistics. (n.d.). <https://www.nigerianstat.gov.ng/elibrary/read/786> Accessed August 28th, 2023
- Nigeria Data Portal (n.d.). https://dataportals.org/portal/nigeria_opendataforafrica Accessed August 28th, 2023

- Nigeria Police Force. (2023). https://www.npf.gov.ng/departments/departments_ict.php. Accessed August 28th, 2023
- Nigeria: Human trafficking factsheet - pathfinders justice initiative. Pathfinders Justice Initiative - A Social Justice Initiative. (2023). Retrieved from <https://pathfindersji.org/nigeria-human-trafficking-factsheet/>
- Pedregosa, F., Varoquaux, G., Gramfort, A., Michel, V., Thirion, B., Grisel, O., Blondel, M., Prettenhofer, P. and Weiss, R., Dubourg, V., Vanderplas, J., Passos, A., Cournapeau, D., Brucher, M., Perrot, M. & Duchesnay, E., (2011), *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, vol 12, 12, pp. 2825-2830, 2011.
- Ranasinghe, P. (2022). Cesare Beccaria and the Aesthetic Knowledge of On Crimes and Punishments. *Law Critique* 34, 127–144 . <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10978-022-09321-6>
- Roth, Mitchel P. (2014). *An Eye for an Eye: A Global History of Crime and Punishment*. Reaktion Books. ISBN 978-1-78023-359-8.
- Rui N., Jinfeng L., & Biao H, (2022). A review On reinforcement learning: Introduction and applications in industrial process control, *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, Volume 139, 2020, 106886, ISSN 0098-1354, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compchemeng.2020.106886>.
- Russell, S. J., & Norvig, P. (2016) *Artificial Intelligence: A Modern Approach*: Pearson.
- Saleh-Hanna, V., Ume, C., Affor, C., Agomoh, U., Agozino, B., Akporherhe, C., Anagaba, S. M., Elechi, O. O., Eribo, O., Nagel, M., Odibo, I., & Sudbury, J. (2008). An Evolution Of The Penal System: Criminal Justice In Nigeria. In *Colonial Systems of Control: Criminal Justice in Nigeria* (pp. 55–68). University of Ottawa Press. <https://doi.org/10.2307/j.ctt1ckph37.7>
- Saminu, I. & Mohammed, S. (2022). Understanding Kidnapping and its effects on Nigeria's national security.
- Siegel, L. (2015). *Criminology: Theories, Patterns, and Typologies*. Cengage Learning. p. 191.
- Simon H., (2010). "Their Days are Spent in Gambling and Loafing, Pimping for Prostitutes, and Picking Pockets": Male Juvenile Delinquents on Lagos Island, Nigeria, 1920s-60s', *Journal of Family History*, 35(1), 2010, 48-70;
- Statista (2020), *Population in Africa, by country 2020*. Statista.
- Sumner, C., ed. (2004). *The Blackwell Companion to Criminology*. Wiley. ISBN 9780631220923.
- U.S. Department of State. (n.d.).(2013). Chapter 6. foreign terrorist organizations. U.S. Department of State. Retrieved from <https://2009-2017.state.gov/j/ct/rls/crt/2013/224829.htm>
- "Unimate." *Encyclopaedia Britannica*. (2008.) *Encyclopaedia Britannica Online*. 08 Oct. 2008.
- van Dijk, J. J. M., & de Waard, J. (1991). A two-dimensional typology of crime prevention projects: With a bibliography. *Criminal justice abstracts*, 483-503.
- Velasco, C. (2022), *Cybercrime and Artificial Intelligence*. An overview of the work of international organizations on criminal justice and the international applicable instruments JO - ERA Forum, SP - 109 EP - 126 VL - 23 SN - 1863-9038 UR - <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12027-022-00702-z> TY - JOUR
- Williams, P. (2014). 'Nigerian Criminal Organizations', in Letizia Paoli (ed.), *The Oxford Handbook of Organized Crime*, Oxford Handbooks <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199730445.013.033>.